

Sample 11a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0005
	{Si}	20.9
	{Fe}	18.9
	{Ca}	17.8
	{Al, Ca}	9.2
	{Si, Ca HIP}	7.5
	{Al, Si}	3.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.3
	{Ca, Fe}	2.9
	{Mg, Ca}	1.8
	{S, Ca}	1.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.4
	{Mg}	1.3
	{Mg, Si}	1.0
	{Mg, Fe}	1.0
	{Si, Fe}	0.9
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.7
	{Al, Si, K}	0.7
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Al}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Na, Si}	0.1
	{Si, K}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Ti}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	6.1
Pellet	1.7
Ore preparation undifferentiated	9.5
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	3.1
BOF converter slag	13.4
BOF converter slag slopping	2.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.8
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	8.8
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	2.3
Olivine flux	0.5
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	4.8
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.8
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	9.6
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	3.5
Carbon rich - other	4.5
Cement or BOF converter	1.6
Cement	2.3
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.4
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	18.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	3.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.7

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	17.3
Site - ore / hot metal	3.1
Site - slag	26.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.7
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	4.8
Site - flux / refractory	0.8
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	9.6
Site - carbon-rich other	3.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	4.5
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.6
Urban	2.9
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	18.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	3.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.1
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.7

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 11b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0003
	{Si}	41.8
	{Fe}	13.5
	{Ca}	13.4
	{Si, Ca HiP}	5.4
	{Al, Si}	4.8
	{Al, Ca}	4.6
	{Ca, Fe}	2.5
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.4
	{S, Ca}	1.5
	{Mg, Si}	1.3
	{Mg, Ca}	0.9
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Mg, Fe}	0.7
	{Si, Fe}	0.7
	{Mg}	0.6
	{Al}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Si, K}	0.2
	{Na, Si}	0.2
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.1
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.1
	{S}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	4.1
Pellet	1.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	5.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	2.0
BOF converter slag	8.1
BOF converter slag slopping	1.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.7
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	3.9
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.5
Olivine flux	0.6
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	4.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.2
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	29.2
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	2.3
Carbon rich - other	3.0
Cement or BOF converter	1.2
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	27.9
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	1.8
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.8

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	10.3
Site - ore / hot metal	2.0
Site - slag	14.9
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	4.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.2
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	29.2
Site - carbon-rich other	2.3
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	3.0
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.2
Urban	0.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	27.9
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	1.8
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.8

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 11c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0087
	{Fe}	20.6
	{Si}	19.2
	{Ca}	18.1
	{Si, Ca HiP}	9.0
	{Al, Ca}	8.5
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.7
	{Ca, Fe}	3.3
	{Al, Si}	2.4
	{S, Ca}	2.2
	{Mg, Ca}	1.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.5
	{Mg, Fe}	1.4
	{Mg}	1.0
	{Si, Fe}	1.0
	{Mg, Si}	0.6
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Al}	0.5
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Al, Si, K}	0.4
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Na, Si}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mn}	0.1
	{Si, K}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	7.0
Pellet	1.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	9.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	3.7
BOF converter slag	18.2
BOF converter slag slopping	0.9
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.7
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	7.3
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.4
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.7
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.7
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.2
Coal and cokes or soil	11.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	6.5
Carbon rich - other	6.4
Cement or BOF converter	1.4
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	11.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	5.6
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.3
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.5

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	17.7
Site - ore / hot metal	3.7
Site - slag	28.1
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.2
Site - flux / slag	3.7
Site - flux / refractory	0.7
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.2
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	11.5
Site - carbon-rich other	6.5
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	6.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.4
Urban	0.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	11.8
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	5.6
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels